

HARMLESS

Safe and Sustainable Innovation Approach (SSIA) & Decision Support System (DSS)

Blanca Suarez-Merino, Susan Dekkers

Final Webinar
11 March 2025 Online

Safe and Sustainable Innovation Approach (SSIA)

 OECD
Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development

ENV/JM/MONO(2020)36/REV1

Unclassified English - Or. English
22 December 2020

ENVIRONMENT DIRECTORATE
JOINT MEETING OF THE CHEMICALS COMMITTEE AND THE WORKING PARTY ON
CHEMICALS, PESTICIDES AND BIOTECHNOLOGY

Moving Towards a Safe(r) Innovation Approach (SIA) for More Sustainable
Nanomaterials and Nano-enabled Products

Series on the Safety of Manufactured Nanomaterials
No. 96

HARMLESS SSbD Approach

- Based on previous EU initiatives (NanoReg2, CaLIBRAte, GRACIOUS)
- Builds on three pillars: safer materials and products, safer production processes and safer use and end-of-life
- It is a lean stage - gate model with an implemented life cycle thinking approach
- Takes into account safety and sustainability
- Includes design principles and tools

HARMLESS SSbD Approach Scope

System Boundaries of the HARMLESS FRAMEWORK

Overview of the HARMLESS SSbD Approach

DESIGN PRINCIPLES

Intrinsic safety assessment

Ideation & business case	Lab scale	Pilot scale
Identify legal restrictions applying to the components of the material.		
Identify and prioritise alternatives to Group A chemicals [2], if possible. If not possible, document alternatives that were tested and reasons for discard.		
Review intrinsic properties linked to early warnings : <ul style="list-style-type: none">•High aspect ratio nanomaterial•Persistency, widespread use•Novelty•Heavy metals and other general risk assessment groups	Cost-effective testing of AdMa e.g., using IATA and NAMs: 1. Identify hazard bands of components*, 2. Prioritise endpoints to test accordingly	Test the AdMa or AdMa-enabled product on phys-chem and hazard properties according to ISO standards and OECD TG for regulatory compliance.

**Using for example the Substance Information System (SIS) available on TNO Diamonds platform (diamonds.tno.nl/sis) or the ECHA database*

SSbD Approach

SSbD Decision Support System (DSS)

Objectives of the SSbD Decision Support System

Build a user-friendly Decision Support System based on SSbD Approach

- Industrial designers
- Advanced (nano)materials (complex HARNs & MC ENMs)
- Innovation stages and all life cycle stages
- Integration knowledge, models and data

IDEATION & BUSINESS CASE PHASE

AMEA

(Advanced Materials Earliest Assessment)

- Material categorisation
- DSS applicability testing
- Generic design principles generation

IDEATION & BUSINESS CASE PHASE

WASP

(Warning flags, design Advice, Screening Priorities)

- Early warnings on safety and sustainability
- Tailored design principles
- Specific assessment advice

LAB PHASE

ASDI

(Alternative SSbD Inspector)

- Comparison of SSbD versions
- Selection of best candidate to proceed to pilot phase

PILOT PHASE

Status Wheel

(Overview of all SSbD aspects)

- More detailed assessment of the selected SSbD version
- Use of tailored predictive modelling

If DSS applicable

Descriptors prioritization & assessment advice triggering

Assessment advice for selected SSbD version

QUALITATIVE ASSESSMENT

DATA AVAILABILITY & QUANTITATIVE ASSESSMENT

AMEA = Advanced Material Earliest Assessment

AMEA questions

Diamonds³

Welcome Susan

Dashboard HARMLESS SSbD-DSS Scan

Three questions:

1. Does it contain/consist of particles?
2. Is it nano-enabled?
3. Is it considered advanced?

Resulting AMEA category

Advanced Nano-enabled Material Consisting of Particles (AdNmCp)

- Consists of particles
- Nano-enabled
- Advanced

<https://diamonds.tno.nl/projects/amea>

Environmental Science Nano

PAPER

View Article Online
View Journal | View Issue

Check for updates

Advanced materials earliest assessment (AMEA)[†]

Cite this: *Environ. Sci.: Nano*, 2024, 11, 2948

Wendel Wohlleben,¹ Michael Persson,² Blanca Suarez-Merino,³ Anders Baun,⁴ Veronica Di Battista,⁵ Susan Dekkers,⁶ Eugene P. van Someren,⁷ Dirk Broßell,¹ Burkhard Stahlmecke,⁸ Martin Wiemann,⁹ Otmär Schmid¹ and Andrea Haase¹

AMEA 2.1 - Advanced Material Earliest Assessment

AMEA is the first step in the HARMLESS SSbD-DSS workflow.

AMEA 2.1 is an online tool, developed by HARMLESS, that helps industry by means of three simple questions with their Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) choices for advanced materials (AdMa) in the earliest phases of innovation.

<https://doi.org/10.1039/D3EN00831B>

AMEA = Advanced Material Earliest Assessment

AMEA advice

SSbD Advice for category: and Innovation Stage:

Advanced Nano-enabled material Consisting of Particles (AdNmCp)
Ideation / Discovery & Scoping

	Phase Characterization:	Guidance for Assessment:
Exposure during lifecycle	A market need has been identified and a design is being developed for a certain P-A-R. Design principles are key to guide the innovation	Design Principles: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consider EoL, design for circularity • Describe P-A-R = product, application, region (World_Business_Council_for_Sustainable_Development 2018) and qualitatively identify potential hot spots
Hazard	Design principles focus on warning signs from late lessons to early warnings: (Harremoës <i>et al.</i> 2001) (Table 2)	Design principles from late lessons to early warnings: (Harremoës <i>et al.</i> 2001) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fibers fitting the WHO criteria (HARM) • Persistency, widespread use • Bioaccumulation, irreversible effects • Heavy metals & other GRA groups • Novelty (= trigger of AdMa discussion)
Sustainability	Design principles of the AdMa product are derived from the sustainability deficiencies of the CoMa product for the same A-R target	

AMEA = Advanced
Material Earliest
Assessment

AMEA advice

Apply the universal design principles.(Subramanian et al. 2023) One of the conventional warning signs, the “novelty”(Harremoës et al. 2001) is in fact the trigger for the entire elaborate concept on AdMa that we discuss here.

If made by advanced manufacturing, consider non-chemical hazards, e.g. process-generated concerns. Examples include the intense laser radiation used in the selective laser sintering process of powder-based 3D-printing, or large-scale robots that are used for 3D printing of concrete on construction sites.

If AdMa with multiple components (MC), transformation is a bigger issue than with single substances.(Abdolahpur Monikh et al. 2023) One should characterize the rate of release and form of release, which may not be identical to the originally synthesized material, e.g. preferential leaching from advanced composite materials, or unintentional triggering of the rare “active” AdMa.(Amorim et al. 2023) All composites are MC by definition.

If AdMa with multiple components (MC), hazards must be identified initially from the hazard of each component, even if mixture effects have to be considered at higher TRL.(Abdolahpur Monikh et al. 2023, Amorim et al. 2023) E.g. on aerogel-glassfiber-mats, one may initially screen for the hazard of the glassfiber and separately for hazard of the aerogel, where the later can be approximated by the most similar CoMa without the extreme porosity. One should, in later phases, perform hazard screenings not on the originally synthesized material but on the released entities. This was originally demonstrated on nano-composite materials. (Wohlleben et al. 2011, Saber et al. 2012, Gomez et al. 2014, Saber et al. 2016, Amorim et al. 2018) A case study is given in the AMEA paper (see introduction pages).

If AdMa, apply similarity tools & rankings to assess if AdMa versions are significantly different from each other and from CoMa. If not, the design space is less restricted in the next phase, and can be guided by performance and cost. If they are significantly different, trade-offs must be weighed, which will require dedicated tools during the lab phase, before pilot phase (to avoid investment decisions leading to failure).

If AdMa, one must provide additional controls (QA/QC) that the methods are appropriate, e.g. by using several methods with complementary measurement principles. For the prioritized endpoints, screenings tests of extrinsic properties should be compatible with or derived from guidances or test guidelines, but do not need to fulfil guideline requirements and do not need GLP status.

If nano-enabled and consisting of particles (upper right quadrant in Figure 1 and Figure 2), appropriate methods must be used for structural similarity (e.g. nanoQSARs, although these may not be fully validated), in phys-chem characterization and in the testing of extrinsic properties (e.g. screenings derived from nano-specific test guidelines,(Abdolahpur Monikh et al. 2018) IATAs for selection of most relevant properties.(Stone et al. 2020, Braakhuis et al. 2021, Murphy et al. 2021, Di Cristo et al. 2022)) Tests may, but do not need to fulfil guideline requirements, and do not need GLP status, if the GLP impacts speed and costs.

The AMEA advice, LICARA, STM, NEQ and other existing tools were used to develop

WASP

a simplified method using less information in early innovation phases (consisting of 12 questions)

The **SSbD-DSS** supports you in the implementation of the above **AMEA** advice by guiding you through other tools, such as **WASP** and **ASDI**. If you started **AMEA** from the **SSbD-DSS**, simply press "Save & Next" and "Return to the DSS". If you started AMEA as stand-alone tool your can find the SSbD-DSS here:

<https://diamonds.tno.nl/harmlesspublic/decision-support-system>

WASP = Warning flags,
design Advice,
Screening Priorities

WASP questions

Diamonds ³

Welcome Susan

Logout

Dashboard

HARMLESS SSbD-DSS

Scan

Back

Questions

Results

1

Safety
(Exposure)

2

Safety
(Hazard)

3

Sustainability
Aspects

4

Early
Warnings
and
Advice

1. Is your material in powder form or can it release dust or aerosols?

Is it possible that the material or product becomes airborne or that it releases dust that becomes airborne?

Yes

No

2. Is consumer exposure foreseen?

12 questions in sections:
Safety (Exposure)
Safety (Hazard) and
Sustainability Aspects

WASP = Warning flags,
design Advice,
Screening Priorities

WASP questions

Question	
1	Does the material itself or its production, manufacturing, use or end of life generate inhalable dust or aerosols?
2	Is exposure to consumers or the general population expected?
3	Is occupational exposure via inhalation expected?
4	Is there more than one form of expected human exposure (i.e. different chemical composition or particle size)?
5	Is wide-dispersive use foreseen, based on the sector, product and final application?
6	What is the tonnage assumed to calculate the Expected Commercial Value (ECV) (i.e. large scale production)?
7	Is there exposure for any environmental compartment expected?
8	Is the material expected to be persistent? If yes, does the material contain fibres with a critical morphology?
9	Is the material expected to show high/enhanced reactivity?
10	Is the material a multicomponent material?
11	Is the material and/or its chemical components expected to be hazardous (human health or environment)?
12	Will your novel material impact SDG Target 3.9, 6.3, 6.4, 7.2, 7.3, 9.4, 11.6, 12.2, 12.4, 12.5, 13.1, 14.1 or 14.3?

WASP = Warning flags,
design Advice,
Screening Priorities

WASP results

Diamonds³ Welcome Susan [Logout](#)

Dashboard HARMLESS SSbD-DSS Scan

← Back WASP 2.1 Introduction WASP 2.1 Questions **WASP 2.1 Results**

WASP 2.1 - Warning flags, design Advice & Screening Prioritization

Question	Answered
1. Does the material itself or its production, manufacturing, use or end of life generate inhalable dust or aerosols?	Yes
<p>Design Advice (for Ideation & Business case phase) Warning: Inhalation exposure is likely.</p> <p>To avoid this, instead of using dry powders, suspending nanomaterials in liquids or dispersions can reduce the risk of inhalation.</p> <p>Also, encapsulating nanomaterials in a matrix can significantly reduce exposure (embedding the nanomaterial in another substance may make it less likely to become airborne.</p> <p>Investigate ways to contain the dust or aerosols from the material, making sure it is not released to the environment or comes in contact with workers or consumers' breathing zone.</p>	<p>Descriptors (for Lab phase; use as rows in ASDI) GRACIOUS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Particle size (what they are) [TEM (OECD TG 125)] • Surface area (what they are) [BET (OECD TG 124)] • Composition (what they are) [ICP-MS (TG 15)] • Dissolution (inhalation IATA) [Dissolution in lung lining and phagolysosomal fluid ISO/TR 19057: 2017, OECD TG 318] • Reactivity (inhalation IATA) (a-cellular ROS) [FRAS (Gandon et al. 2017), DCFH2-DA (Reiniers et al. 2021, EPR (ISO 2017), Carbonylation)] <p>OTHER</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dustiness [CEN – EN 15051, EN17199:2019] • Respirable fraction [Respirable size fraction of airborne particles (CEN – EN 481)]
<p>Assessment Advice (for Lab phase) Follow Gracious inhalation IATA</p>	
Question	Answered
2. Is exposure to consumers or the general population expected?	Yes

Design advice

Assessment advice

Default descriptors

ASDI =
Alternative SSbD
Design Inspector

ASDI materials to compare

1. Start with the design space (properties in which the SSbD versions differ)

Diamonds³

Dashboard HARMLESS SSbD-DSS SSbD Decision Support System Projects

Project dashboard General information Innovation stage Nano material ASDI Measurements Scans Visualisations Comparisons

Getting started Matrix input Heatmap Settings

AdMa Advanced Materials					ReMa		CoMa		
	Advanced material (AdMa)	Advanced material (AdMa)	Advanced material (AdMa)	Advanced material (AdMa)	Advanced material (AdMa)	Reference material (ReMa)	Reference material (ReMa)	Conventional material (CoMa)	
Name	LaCoNi(5)	LaCoNi(8)	LaCoNi_Pd	LaCoNi_Pt	LaNi(22)	NiFe408	NiFe204	CeO2_Pd	
Design Space	Granulometry: diameter	nm	nm	nm	nm	nm	nm	nm	
Design Space	Composition: Nickel (IC)	wt%	wt%	wt%	wt%	wt%	wt%	wt%	
Design Space	Composition: Cobalt (IC)	wt%	wt%	wt%	wt%	wt%	wt%	wt%	
Design Space	Band gap (in silico) [eV]	eV	eV	eV	eV	eV	eV	eV	
Design Space	Specific surface area (BET)	m2/g	m2/g	m2/g	m2/g	m2/g	m2/g	m2/g	

Here, 5 different Advanced Material designs, 2 Reference Materials, and 1 Coventional Material are entered into the Alternative SSbD Design Inspector (ASDI) (currently for 5 descriptors ...)

ASDI =
Alternative SSbD
Design Inspector

ASDI matrix

2. Select other relevant descriptors based on WASP results from ideation phase (from a default list based on the GRACIOUS IATAs & SDG target indicators)

Diamonds³

Dashboard HARMLESS SSbD-DSS SSbD Decision Support System Projects

Project dashboard General information Innovation stage Nano material ASDI Measurements Scans Visualisations Comparisons

Getting started Matrix input Heatmap Settings

		Advanced material (AdMa)	Reference material (ReMa)	Reference material (ReMa)	Conventional material (CoMa)					
	Name	LaCoNi(5)	LaCoNi(8)	LaCoNi_Pd	LaCoNiPt	LaNi(22)	NiFe408	NiFe204	CeO2_Pd	
Human Safety Occupational	Leechable Ni mass after	wt%	wt%	wt%	wt%	wt%	wt%	wt%	wt%	
Human Safety Occupational	Leechable Co mass after	wt%	wt%	wt%	wt%	wt%	wt%	wt%	wt%	
Human Safety Occupational	Bioreactivity by EPR-CP1	spins/mL	spins/mL	spins/mL	spins/mL	spins/mL	spins/mL	spins/mL	spins/mL	
Human Safety Occupational	Bioreactivity by DCFH2-L	mg/L	mg/L	mg/L	mg/L	mg/L	mg/L	mg/L	mg/L	
Human Safety Occupational	Bioreactivity by FRAS (G)	nmoITEU/L	nmoITEU/L	nmoITEU/L	nmoITEU/L	nmoITEU/L	nmoITEU/L	nmoITEU/L	nmoITEU/L	
Human Safety Occupational	Bioreactivity after transf	nmoITEU/mg	nmoITEU/mg	nmoITEU/mg	nmoITEU/mg	nmoITEU/mg	nmoITEU/mg	nmoITEU/mg	nmoITEU/mg	

Show Support

ASDI =
Alternative SSbD
Design Inspector

ASDI results

	LaCoNi(5) Advanced material (AdMa)	LaCoNi(8) Advanced material (AdMa)	LaCoNi_Pd Advanced material (AdMa)	LaCoNi_Pt Advanced material (AdMa)	LaCoNi(16) Advanced material (AdMa)	ZnNiFe408 Reference material (ReMa)	NiFe204 Reference material (ReMa)	CeO2_Pd Conventional material (CoMa)
Performance	Red	Green	Green	Green	Red	Red	Red	Green
Design Space	Grey	Grey	Grey	Grey	Grey	Grey	Grey	Grey
Human Safety Occupational	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
Environmental Safety	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green
Sustainability	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red

For each dimension (main row), one sees the individual descriptors (small row) and their color-coded values. Rather than a forced color, we believe showing the individual results provides more insight into the coherence within a dimension

ASDI =
Alternative SSbD
Design Inspector

ASDI results

Overview Heatmap

Human Safety Occupational

	LaCoNi(5) Advanced material (AdMa)	LaCoNi(8) Advanced material (AdMa)	LaCoNi_Pd Advanced material (AdMa)	LaCoNi_Pt Advanced material (AdMa)	LaCoNi(16) Advanced material (AdMa)	ZnNiFe408 Reference material (ReMa)	NiFe204 Reference material (ReMa)	CeO2_Pd Conventional material (CoMa)
Leechable Ni mass % after 7 days in PSF	Green	Grey	Grey	Grey	Red	Green	Grey	Green
Leechable Co mass % after 7 days in PSF	Grey	Red	Red	Red	Grey	Green	Green	Green
ROS generation by EPR-CPH at 10*15g/L	Grey	Grey	Grey	Grey	Red	Grey	Green	Grey
Bioreactivity (DCFH2-DA RPF)	Grey	Red	Green	Red	Green	Grey	Grey	Grey
Bioreactivity (FRAS RPF)	Green	Green	Green	Green	Grey	Red	Grey	Green
Bioreactivity after transformation by FRAS	Grey	Red	Grey	Grey	Red	Green	Green	Grey

LICARA 4.0 Questions

Diamonds³ Welcome Susan Logout

Dashboard HARMLESS SSbD-DSS Scan

← Back Introduction **Nano Scan** Result

1 Nano Product and Legislation 2 Environmental Benefits 3 Economic Benefits 4 Societal Benefits 5 Public Health & Environmental Risks 6 Occupational Health Risks - Stoffenmanager 7 Consumer Health Risks

Please answer the five questions below about the type of nanomaterial and application.

1. Which nanomaterial will be used?

Other

Please specify additional nano subtype or indications / properties:

2. In which type of application is the nanomaterial be used?

Batteries

3. Is this a completely new product with a new functionality (which cannot easily be compared with a conventional product)?

No

If not, what conventional product is being replaced by the new nanoproduct? (this can also be 'doing nothing')

New features/improvements:

- No need for Stoffenmanager nano
 - STMnano hazard band included
 - NEQ exposure band included
- Visualisation (next slide)

LICARA 4.0 Results

Visualisation in Status Wheel

- Point estimate including uncertainty
- Overview of various SSbD dimensions
 - Human Health Safety
 - Environmental Safety
 - Environmental sustainability
 - Socio-economic sustainability

Other pilot phase tools

More complex, quantitative models & testing methods (NAMs), such as:

- GRACIOUS Tier 2 testing methods
- In vitro NAMs
- Quantitative predictive exposure and hazard models

Future feature: Adding the outcomes of these models & methods to the Status Wheel by replacing or adding new segments

Photo by thr3 eyes on Unsplash

Project 07-07-2021

Hotspot Scan

The Hotspot Scan is a public tool that allows a systematic and efficient assessment of potential hotspots in the life cycle of innovative products. To perform a full LCA can be a time-consuming and challenging task, the HotSpotScan provides an intermediate assessment focusing on the strongest human health and environmental impacts based on establishing all the material flows.

[Read more](#)

Project 14-11-2022

Nano Exposure Quantifier

The Nano Exposure Quantifier (NEQ) is a quantitative exposure assessment tool. It is designed to assist users in the safe-by-design process and decisions to reduce risk as a result from working with manufactured nanomaterials. The NEQ offers a Tiered approach by adapting the questions based on the depth of information the user can provide allowing anywhere between a Tier-1 and a Tier-2 approach.

[Read more](#)

SSbD Approach

SSbD Decision Support System (DSS)

Results of EWS: oxide-perovskites case study (=> pitch)

Tier 0		Tier 1				
(1) Novelty of material	AdMa (not yet on the market; R&D products at Lab Phase)					
In the scope of the EWS						
(2) Does it consist of particles?	Yes (primary particles > 100 nm)					
Route B (hazard first)						
(3) Nano-enabled?	yes					
ISO definition (nanostructured)						
(4) Category	Automotive catalyst					
Comparison with conventional automotive catalysts						
		Question	Simple		Elaborated	Final
		8a. Persistence	no	█		█
		8b. Fibres with critical morphology	NA			
		9. High / enhanced reactivity	yes	█	→ yes	█
		10. Multicomponent	yes	█	→ yes	█
		11. Hazardous for human health or environment	yes	█	→ yes	█
		1. Dust / aerosol release	yes	█	→ yes	█
		2. Consumers or general population exposure	no	█		█
		3. Occupational exposure	yes	█	→ yes	█
		4. More than one form of human exposure	no	█		█
		5. Wide-dispersive use	no	█		█
		6. Assumed tonnage	> 1000 t	█	→ yes	█
		7. Environmental exposure	no	█		█
		12g. SDG 11.6 Air quality	yes, pos.	█	→ +1	Total: 0
		12h. SDG 12.2 Natural resources	yes, neg.	█	→ -1	
		13. Which legislation		█		
		14. Applicability of legislation	yes	█		
		15. Available / adopted methods	yes	█		

B

A

C

D

Future perspectives DSS

- **Further development pilot phase methods and tools**
- **Possible use of EWS in OECD Early4AdMa Tier 1**
- **Develop customized tools for industrial companies (e.g. BASF)**
- **Develop non-particle specific tools (e.g. PLANETS)**

Thanks for your attention!

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 953183

More information?

Visit the HARMLESS website:

<https://www.harmless-project.eu/>

Visit the DIAMONDS website:

<https://diamonds.tno.nl/>

Registering TODAY will give direct access to the pre-launch demo version

Preprints of our publications the SSbD approach and DSS:

<https://doi.org/10.22541/au.174077018.85147151/v1>

<https://doi.org/10.22541/au.173991289.98651419/v1>

HARMLESS

FOLLOW US TO NEVER MISS A THING!

LinkedIn

Twitter

www.harmless-project.eu